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ABSTRACTBOOK

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Evaluation of the influence of bile acids on clindamycin hydrochloride permeability using *in vitro* PAMPA skin model

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INTRODUCTION

Clindamycin, a lincosamide antibiotic, is widely used in therapy of mild to moderate cases of acne and skin infections. Although widely used in dermatology, the major issue of conventional clindamycin topical formulations for effective treatment is the hydrophilic nature of clindamycin (logP 0.5), not suitable for skin penetration and accumulation in the pilosebaceous structures as lipophilic environment [1]. Clindamycin is a water-soluble weak base, which is mostly in ionized form at physiological pH and it is usually classified in class III of the Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS), with good aqueous solubility and poor membrane permeability. Several vesicular and particulate nanodelivery systems of clindamycin have been developed in order to enhance the delivery of clindamycin to the intended site of action after topical application [2].

The use of bile acids in both conventional dosage forms and novel micellar, vesicular, and polymer-based drug delivery systems has been increasingly investigated due to their biocompatibility and specific physicochemical properties [3]. Namely, bile acids may act as permeation enhancers not only by increasing the solubility of hydrophobic drugs, but also by increasing the fluidity of biological membranes. The most common interaction of bile acids with drugs is ion-pairing, and the formed complexes may have either higher or lower polarity compared to the drug molecule

itself. The formation of hydrophobic ionic complexes with bile salts is particularly significant for drugs belonging to the BCS class III.

The aim of this study was to determine the influence of cholic acid (CA) and deoxycholic acid (DCA) and clindamycin ionization state at different pH values on its permeation using *in vitro* parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA) model. The objective was also to evaluate the molecular mechanisms involved in interactions between the studied drug and bile acids.

METHODS

Skin-PAMPA permeability assay

The following experimental groups were designed: Clin – clindamycin 200 µM, ClinCA10, ClinCA50 and ClinCA100 - clindamycin 200 µM with CA in concentrations of 10, 50 and 100 µM, and ClinDCA10, ClinDCA50 and ClinDCA100 - clindamycin 200 µM with DCA in concentrations of 10, 50 and 100 µM, respectively. All experiments were performed in triplicates at two pH values: 5.5 (normal skin) and 6.5 (inflamed skin).

Hydrophobic MultiScreen PVDF 96-well microfiltration plates with a diameter pore of 0.45 µm were used as the acceptor plates and carriers for artificial membrane (17 µL of a 35% v/v solution of isopropyl myristate/silicone oil mixture (3:7) in n-hexane). Skin-PAMPA assay procedure

was initiated by filling the acceptor plate wells with 200 μL of buffers pH 5.5 and 6.5, while 300 μL of test compound solutions in the same buffers were added to the donor sections of the MultiScreen Transport Receiver Plate. The assembled plates were incubated at room temperature on an orbital shaker (50 rpm) for 12 h. After the incubation time, samples from both compartments were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 210 nm for clindamycin concentrations. The apparent permeability coefficient ($P_{\text{app-skin}}$) was calculated using the measured concentrations, volumes of donor and acceptor compartment solutions, the surface area of the membrane and time.

Structural modelling and geometry optimization

3D structures of clindamycin hydrochloride and bile acids (CA and DCA) and their complexes were prepared using the Chem3D Ultra software. Molecular geometries were optimized using MM2 force field calculations.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using one-factor ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test in IBM SPSS Statistics software with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows apparent permeability coefficients ($P_{\text{app-skin}}$) as the measure of permeability of clindamycin at pH 5.5 and 6.5. Clindamycin permeability was higher than 1.5×10^{-6} cm/s in all studied groups, indicating good membrane permeability in this model. The effect of pH on clindamycin permeability was not statistically significant, although it was higher at pH 6.5 as expected. The highest values of clindamycin permeability were achieved after addition of bile acids in the concentration of 100 μM . This was particularly expressed in the case of CA at pH 6.5, where the permeability coefficient of clindamycin was statistically significant higher after addition of CA in concentration of 100 μM than when it was used in concentrations of 50 μM ($p = 0.03$) and 10 μM ($p = 0.02$).

	Permeability [$P_{\text{app-skin}} \times 10^{-6}$] [cm/s]	
	pH 5.5	pH 6.5
Clin	9,04 \pm 1,26	9,19 \pm 2,32
ClinCA10	6,79 \pm 1,31	6,57 \pm 0,58
ClinCA50	7,53 \pm 1,82	6,72 \pm 1,21
ClinCA100	9,76 \pm 0,36	11,79 \pm 2,75
ClinDCA10	7,72 \pm 2,08	8,44 \pm 0,61
ClinDCA50	8,21 \pm 1,74	8,11 \pm 1,99
ClinDCA100	9,20 \pm 1,07	10,16 \pm 0,81

Table 1. The permeability of clindamycin after 12 h incubation at room temperature at pH 5.5 and 6.5

The interactions of clindamycin hydrochloride and bile acids were investigated also by molecular mechanics calculations (MM2). The total energies, as the sum of stretching, bending, torsion, electrostatic, and non-bonded interaction energies, were calculated. The minimized total energies of clindamycin, CA and DCA were 29.30

kcal/mol, 52.16 kcal/mol, and 48.81 kcal/mol, respectively. The total energies of both complexes were lower than the sum of the potential energies of the two single components, indicating that the formation of the complexes induced a stabilization of the system. Clindamycin/CA complex was shown to be more stable (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Geometrically optimized three-dimensional structures of (A) clindamycin/CA and (B) clindamycin/DCA complexes

CONCLUSION

The permeability of clindamycin hydrochloride depends largely on the addition of bile acids, especially in the higher concentrations (100 μM) and at pH of 6.5. CA exerted more pronounced effect than DCA, which may be explained by formation of more stable hydrophobic complexes with the studied antibiotic drug.

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4th European Conference on Pharmaceutics

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We are looking forward to seeing you at the 4th European Conference on Pharmaceutics in Marseille in 2023.

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